

PROBLEMS OF COMBINING WORK IN THE LABOR LAW OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Khojabekov Muftulla Jolmurza uly,

Senior lecturer at the Department of Labor Law

Tashkent State University of Law

Muftulla_khojabekov@mail.ru

+998907275767

Annotation: This article is devoted to the main directions of legal regulation of combining jobs in Uzbekistan. Based on the object and subject of the article, it notes that at present the combining regime raises some difficult issues that require a more flexible approach. In particular, the possibility of women on maternity leave to work part-time, the pros and cons of combining work, and others. The methodological basis of the article was the modern achievements of the theory of knowledge. In the process of research, general philosophical, theoretical, general philosophical methods (dialectics, system method, analysis, synthesis, analogy, deduction, observation and modeling), traditional legal methods, as well as methods used in concrete sociological research were used.

Key words: combining job, maternity leave, advantages of combining job, disadvantages of combining job, problems of combining work.

Introduction

Issues related to the regulation of the labor of persons working part-time are still relevant to the theory and practice of labor law. The main feature of the legal status of a part-time worker is that he is in at least two labor relations (main and part-time). This allows you to highlight the part-time worker in a special category of workers.

At the present stage, there is a need to take a closer look at this institution of labor law, taking into account its quality and those objective requirements that modern forms of labor organization impose on combining job, and in a discussion order to consider possible directions for the further development of this institution of labor law.

It is known that on October 28, a new Labor Code was signed, which will enter into force on April 30, 2023. Unlike the current code, the new Labor Code contains a rule regarding the work of part-time workers. However, the main regulator of combining job has been and remains the Regulation on the procedure for combining job and the combination of professions and positions.

Under combining job, as indicated in Article 432 of the new Labor Code, one should understand the performance, in addition to his main job, by an employee of another regular paid job on the terms of a separate employment contract in his spare time from his main job.

Based on the content of the Regulation, the following main features of combining job can be distinguished:

- 1) Performance of other (besides the main) regular, paid work;
- 2) Work is carried out in free time from the main work;
- 3) The work is performed under an employment contract on combining job;
- 4) The number of employers (both legal entities and individuals) with whom an employee has the right to conclude an employment contract on combining job is not limited by law;

5) Work can be performed both for a single employer at the main place of work on the terms of internal combination, and for other employers on the terms of external combination;

6) The employment contract contains an indication that the work performed is part-time.

For an employer, combining job is good because it allows you to close the need for an employee without paying full time. For an employee, combining job is additional income and the opportunity to gain experience in another position. However, it is not always possible for employees to fulfill their intention to work part-time, because there are legislative restrictions on certain persons. In particular:

Persons under the age of eighteen;

In jobs with unfavorable working conditions, if the main job of a part-time worker is associated with the same conditions (with the exception of employees of healthcare organizations);

As an employee (specialist) of the road transport safety service;

Employees (except for technical and service personnel) of the Administration of the President and the Office of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, heads of government bodies, their deputies and heads of structural units, the Chairman and members of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, except as provided by decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan ;

Khokims of regions, districts and cities and their deputies;

Specialists of public administration bodies in organizations subordinate or controlled by one another, with the exception of doctors employed in health authorities and teachers employed in education authorities;

Other persons (employees) who, in accordance with the law, are prohibited

from working part-time.

The author agrees with this list of persons, with the exception of the last category. Considering how long ago the Regulation on part-time workers was adopted, as well as changes in the labor market, it is already possible to introduce a specific list of prohibitions that do not raise any questions. In addition, according to the author, this Regulation should also be supplemented with a list that would allow combining job only with the written consent of the employer in order to avoid labor disputes. At the same time, the employer should be obliged to justify his refusal in order to prevent abuse of his official authority.

Foreign experience shows which persons should be included in this list. For example, athletes and coaches, law enforcement officials, as well as persons with access to any kind of secrets. Of course, combining job of the above persons should be studied.

The legislation does not restrict women who are on official parental leave in their direct right to early return to work. While on maternity leave, every woman has the legal right to work officially as a combining job.

Often in practice, there is a case of converting combining jobs into the main place of work. If a part-time employee terminates the employment contract at the main place of work, then combining job does not automatically become the main place of work for him. Since the condition of combining job is a mandatory condition of the employment contract, and in accordance with Article 88 of the Labor Code, changes in the terms of the employment contract determined by the parties are allowed only by agreement of the parties and only in writing, the relevant additions indicating that this work has become the main employee, in accordance with the procedure established by labor legislation, must be included in the employment contract.

It should also be noted that not all types of labor activity are considered combining jobs. In accordance with the law, the following activities are not

considered combining jobs:

1. The implementation of scientific or teaching activities, if such activities are not work performed at the main place of work.

2. Creation of works of science, literature and art, payment for which is made in the form of royalties.

3. Performance by an employee, in addition to the main work of other work, without holding a regular position in the same organization, including:

the fulfillment by teachers of general education schools and teachers of professional colleges and academic lyceums of the duties of managing classrooms, laboratories, leading circles, as well as their performance of educational work in excess of the established load;

Pedagogical work with hourly wages for 50 percent of the normal working hours for this type of work;

teaching work of heads of educational institutions in the amount of not more than 50 percent of the total working time provided for by the annual work plan (working time standard) for a teaching position;

the work of engineering and technical workers of organizations to manage the industrial training and practice of students and students;

Duty of medical workers in excess of the established norm of time;

Performance of duties for which, by decisions of the Government, bonuses to the employee's wages are established.

4. Literary work, including work on editing, translating and reviewing individual works, payment for which is made in the form of royalties.

5. Technical, medical, accounting, legal and other expertise (consultation) with a one-time payment.

6. The work of teachers and other pedagogical workers (except for heads) of general education schools, specialized educational institutions, out-of-school educational institutions, teachers and masters of secondary specialized, vocational

educational institutions and other educational institutions equivalent to them in terms of remuneration of workers, concertmasters and accompanists in educational institutions, pedagogical workers (except for heads) of preschool educational institutions and Mehribonlik houses in excess of the established labor norm in the same institution, but not more than 50 percent of the normal working hours for this type of work.

7. Performing the duties of medical consultants in health care institutions for 24 hours per month with a one-time or hourly wage.

8. Supervision of senior research fellows-applicants in research institutions and higher educational institutions, carried out by researchers who are not on the staff of these institutions.

9. Work performed by an employee as an executive in elected positions of central and territorial bodies of political parties, trade unions and public associations, chairman or member of the Supervisory Board or the Board of Directors (managers), managing committee under Production Sharing Agreements, trustee in organizations.

10. Works that are performed on a voluntary basis.

One of the features of an employment contract for combining job is the establishment of an additional basis for terminating an employment contract with persons working part-time under an employment contract for an indefinite period. They can be dismissed in case of hiring an employee for whom this work will be the main one (Article 100 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan) and, unlike a part-time worker, a workbook will be kept for him. The labor legislation does not provide for a notice period for the upcoming dismissal. According to the author, the absence of this period in some way violates the rights of part-time workers.

Conclusion

Summing up the consideration of the problem of the normative definition

of combining job, we will formulate the following proposals aimed at eliminating the existing shortcomings of labor legislation and improving the efficiency of legal regulation of combining job.

When applying for a combining job (both to the main employer and to another organization not related to the main place of work), one should not forget about the regulatory side: the conclusion of an employment contract with a combining job, the content of this contract, compliance with all conditions prescribed by labor legislation (holidays, benefits, compensation, etc.).

When carrying out a large-scale reform of the legal regulation of labor in the conditions of an emerging labor market, it is appropriate to raise the question of the future fate of the institution of combining job. In other words, the legislation on part-time employment requires full consideration and improvements. Improving the legislation on part-time work and the practice of its application in the calculation of today, it is necessary to predict its future fate in relation to the latest forms of labor organization and adequate legal support regimes.

Persons working combining job may be dismissed on any of the grounds provided for by the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. However, the proposal puts forward the need for a warning about the upcoming termination of the employment contract at least three days in advance.

It is also meaningful to conduct a social and legal experiment in the field of organizing the work of part-time workers in a separate production (industry) or region of the country in order to test the effectiveness of the restrictions and prohibitions applied by labor legislation on combining job.

List of used literature

Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 04/01/1996. National Legislation Database.

Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of the regulation on the procedure for part-time work and combining professions and positions” dated 10/18/2012 No. 297

Nigmatullo o‘g‘li, M. D. (2022). termination of employment contract due to circumstances beyond the control of the parties (theoretical and legal analysis). World Bulletin of Management and Law, 17, 94-97.

Karimjonov, M. (2021). A Disciplinary Responsibility By The Labor Legislation Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan. The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology, 3(05), 121-129.

РАХИМОВ, М. (2021). Covid-19га қарши эмлаш ва ходим ҳуқуқлари. юрист ахборотномаси, 2(4), 75-81.

Юсупов, Н. (2022). Материальная ответственность сторон трудового договора как вид юридической ответственности. Общество и инновации, 3(6/S), 329-335.

Хакбердиев, А. К. (2022). Вопросы применимого права в трудовых отношениях: прекращение трудового договора с работником иностранного посольства. Scientific progress, 3(7), 90-94.

MURODULLAYEV D. MEHNAT SHARTNOMASINING TARAFLAR IXTIYORIGA BOG ‘LIQ BO ‘LMAGAN HOLATLAR BO ‘YICHA BEKOR QILINISHINING UMUMIY TAVSIFI //ЮРИСТ АХБОРОТНОМАСИ. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 54-60.

Shoislomova, S. (2022). Features of Disciplinary Measures in the Labor Legislation of Foreign Countries. International journal of business diplomacy and economy, 1(4), 58-61.

Vaxdatovna, B. X. (2022). Labor legislation of the republic of

belarusuzbekistan: A new stage of development. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(4), 1-9.

Исmoilов, Ш. А. (2020). The last tendencies of liberalization of labor and employment legislation of the republic of uzbekistan. журнал правовых исследований, (special 5).

Rahimqulova, L. (2021). The Procedure For Resolving Individual Labour Disputes In Uzbekistan, Post-Soviet Countries And Some Developed Countries. *Comparative-Legal Analysis. Ilkogretim Online*, 20(3).